

Thiosulphato-Cobalt Complexes. Part II. Thiosulphato-pentacyano-potassium Cobaltiate.

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In a previous communication the preparations and properties of a number of thiosulphato-pentammine cobaltic salts have been described, in which the thiosulphate radicle is a member of the complex positive ion with cobalt as the central atom. Description of a compound in which the thiosulphate group is a constituent of a negative complex ion with cobalt as the central atom forms the subject-matter of the present paper. The action of potassium cyanide solution upon thiosulphato-pentammine cobaltic chloride (*loc. cit.*) has led to the formation of a new type of compound whose constitution can be represented as $K_4[S_2O_3 \cdot Co(CN)_5]$.

This may be regarded as containing a substituted cobalticyanide ion and be termed thiosulphato-pentacyano-potassium cobaltiate. The complex ion thus derived has a negative valency of four and in fact is the first representative of the hitherto unknown type of the complex cobalt salts. Similar substituted ferro- and ferri-cyanides have, however, been described by Hoffmann. These are nitrito-, sulphito-, and arsenito-pentacyano ferrous (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1896, 12, 167) ; nitroso-pentacyano-ferriate (*Annalen*, 1900, 312, 1), and aquo-pentacyano-ferriate (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1896, 12, 150).

The constitution of the above thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltiate has been definitely established by chemical and physical methods. The reaction leading to its formation may be expressed by the following equation :—

The action of sodium nitrite and sodium sulphite solutions upon the thiosulphato-pentammine cobaltic chloride has led to the formation of trinitrito-triammine cobalt and an impure mixture of sodium cobaltisulphite respectively as indicated below :—

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation.—The thiosulphato-pentammine cobaltic chloride was finely powdered and treated with a strong solution of potassium cyanide; there was a strong evolution of ammonia and a deep orange-coloured solution was obtained. The solution was filtered, cooled in ice water and then treated with alcohol drop by drop with constant stirring. A large crop of yellow crystals separated out in a short time. The crystals were filtered, washed with 30 per cent. alcohol and then redissolved in a small quantity of water. The solution was again cooled in ice water and the substance recrystallized by the addition of a few drops of alcohol. The crystals were first washed as before and then with absolute alcohol. They were finally dried in air.

The crystals thus obtained are bright yellow and highly soluble in water. The solution does not give any reaction for cobalt ions and is neutral to litmus. Neither sulphuretted hydrogen nor ammonium sulphide gives any precipitate of cobalt sulphide from its solution. Silver nitrate solution gives a yellow gelatinous precipitate in the cold, but on warming with dilute sulphuric acid it slowly changes into brown silver sulphide. A solution of the substance when boiled with dilute sulphuric acid or strong hydrochloric acid gives a precipitate of sulphur and liberates sulphur dioxide gas but no hydrocyanic acid. On oxidation with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide the whole of the thiosulphate radicle is oxidized to sulphate without any change in the colour of the solution. A freshly prepared solution of the salt gives characteristic precipitates with solutions of salts of the heavy metals as described below—resembling potassium cobalticyanide very closely in this respect.

Silver nitrate solution gives a light yellow gelatinous precipitate in the cold, soluble in ammonia. Cobalt nitrate solution gives a rose-coloured gelatinous precipitate. Copper sulphate solution gives a light green gelatinous precipitate insoluble in dilute acids but soluble in ammonia to a blue solution. Lead nitrate solution gives a cream coloured heavy granular precipitate soluble in dilute acetic acid. With manganous chloride solution no precipitate is obtained—a distinction from potassium cobalticyanide. Mercuric chloride solution gives no precipitate whereas mercurous nitrate solution gives a pale yellow precipitate insoluble in dilute nitric

acid. With nickel sulphate solution a pale green gelatinous precipitate insoluble in dilute sulphuric acid is formed. Zinc sulphate solution gives a light yellow sparingly soluble precipitate which dissolves in hot water and forms a crystalline precipitate on cooling. Cadmium nitrate solution behaves like zinc giving a light yellow sparingly soluble precipitate. The precipitate is soluble in excess of the cadmium salt solution and also in boiling water being again precipitated in a crystalline form from the latter on cooling. Zinc and cadmium possibly give rise to the formation of double salts.

The substance does not react with potassium chromate and potassium ferro- or ferri-cyanide solution. From the properties and reactions described above, it is clear that the substance does not give any cobalt ion, cyanide ion or thiosulphate ion in solution. It contains a complex anion containing thiosulphate and cyanogen radicle with cobalt as the central atom. In solution however it slowly hydrolyses into aquo-pentacyano-cobaltate on warming as it then gives a reddish brown precipitate with silver nitrate solution. This is further confirmed by conductivity measurements. The hydrolysis proceeds thus:—

For analysis the substance was decomposed by heating with hot concentrated sulphuric acid; the solution was diluted and cobalt was precipitated as cobalt sulphide from the solution. The latter was then converted into cobalt sulphate and weighed as such. Potassium was estimated in the filtrate as potassium sulphate. The thiosulphate was estimated by oxidation to sulphate with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide and then by precipitation as barium sulphate. Cyanogen was converted into ammonium salts by heating with strong sulphuric acid and potassium bisulphate and then distilling the ammonia as usual. (Found: Co, 12·85; 13·08; S, 13·94; N, 15·18; K, 33·63. $K_4[S_2O_3Co(CN)_5]$ requires Co, 12·91; S, 14·00; N, 15·31; K, 34·1 per cent.).

Conductivity Measurements.

Following results were obtained with a freshly prepared solution of the substance in conductivity water at 20°C.

ν (dilution)	148.9,	297.8,	595.6,	1191.2
M ,	386.9,	416.2.	483.2,	567.6

A determination at a higher temperature at 26°C gave much higher values which further increased on keeping the solution, specially in contact with the electrodes in the cell—the latter catalytically accelerating the hydrolysis already appreciable at this temperature.

Molecular conductivity for hexammine platinum chloride $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_4$ and potassium ferrocyanide $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ which also furnish a tetravalent complex ion (positive in the case of platinum and negative in the case of iron) in addition to four simple monovalent ions are quoted here for comparison. (Weinland, "Einführung in die Chemie der Komplex-Verbindungen," p. 5).

ν (dilution)	128	256	512	1042
M , for $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ at 25°C.	432	477	520	558

M , for $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_4$ at 25°C 433 485 528

(Werner and Miolati *Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 14, 506.)

Agreement between these values and those obtained for the present substance is sufficiently close to confirm the existence of a tetravalent complex ion in a solution of the latter.

Molecular Weight Determination.

Molecular weight of the substance in aqueous solution was determined by the freezing point method with the following results.

Concentration per 100 gm. of water	Depression.	M . W. found.
2.0560 gm.	0.266°	139.1
1.47 gm.	0.198°	153.6

These two determinations were made in fairly dilute solutions. Theoretically the molecular weight calculated on the assumption that the salt in solution is completely ionized, should have been 91.4. The higher values therefore indicate that even at this dilution the

substance is not completely dissociated. This in fact holds for all salts with polyvalent ions, the dissociation progressing by stages. In the present case the gradual dissociation of the salt in solution can be represented thus:

Apparently the last stage of dissociation was not reached in the present instance. Experiments with further diluted solution were not possible on account of very small depression of the freezing point that would result and vitiate the accuracy of determinations.

Coagulating Power and Absorbability.

A solution having 0.01 mol. per litre was prepared using conductivity water. And its coagulating power was compared against that of a potassium ferrocyanide solution of the same strength upon a positive ferric hydroxide sol with the following results:

One c.c. of the potassium ferrocyanide solution diluted to 2.5 c.c. with water and mixed with 2.5 c.c. of the ferric hydroxide sol coagulated the latter completely in 0.58 secs. Whereas even 0.15 c.c. of the 0.01 M solution of the substance almost instantaneously effected the complete coagulation of the same amount of ferric hydroxide sol under exactly the same conditions. This shows that the coagulating power of the complex negative ion of the substance under examination is much higher than that of the complex ferrocyanide ion with a negative valency of four. The valency of the complex anion of the thiosulphato-compound is therefore likely to be at least as high as that of the ferrocyanide ion (Freundlich, *Koll-Zeit.*, 1922, 31, 243). This is also supported by the charge-reversal effect produced in a ferric hydroxide sol when the latter was mixed with a solution of the substance with a concentration of about 0.02 mol per litre.

Magnetic Susceptibility.—The substance when examined in a Curie's balance was found to be diamagnetic. This is perfectly in agreement with Rosenbohm's results (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1919, 93, 603) who examined a large number of complex metallic or co-ordination compounds and found that almost all the complex

cobaltic compounds thus examined were diamagnetic. That the substance is a definite co-ordination compound is thus placed beyond doubt. All the co-ordinated cobalt compounds, as shown by Welo and Baudisch (*Nature*, 1925, 116, 606), should exhibit diamagnetic susceptibility due to their having closed electronic configurations resembling that of the inert gas krypton as interpreted by Sidgwick in developing his "effective atomic number" rule (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 725).

Action of Sodium Nitrite upon Thiosulphato-pentammine Cobaltic Chloride.

Finely powdered thiosulphato-pentammine cobaltic chloride was digested with warm strong solution of sodium nitrite. The former gradually went into solution with slow evolution of ammonia. The solution after filtration was heated on the water-bath when more ammonia was evolved and a very sparingly soluble yellow product separated out. This was first thoroughly washed with cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air.

On analysis and examination, the substance was found to be pure trinitrito-triammine cobalt $[(NO_2)_3Co(NH_3)_3]$. This affords a very easy and rapid method of preparing pure trinitrito-triammine cobalt. (Found: Co, 28.84; NH_3 , 20.57. $[(NO_2)_3Co(NH_3)_3]$ requires Co, 28.8; NH_3 , 20.56 per cent.).

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